

Information System Security Framework and Vulnerability Assessment for Ethiopian Higher Educational Institution using ISO/IEC 27001

Author Details: Haftom Gebreziagbher

Deputy Director General for Academics, Federal TVET Institute Addis Ababa, Ethiopia

Abstract

Ethiopian government recognized the importance of ICT for the country's development and ICT in education is also expected to be a key catalyst for the transformation of education so as to contribute for the economic prosperity in the country. In Fact, Ethiopian Higher Education Institution (EHEI) embrace BPR, and many studies have been done focusing on reengineering and implementing BPR in EHEI's. However, its focuses was given to the investigation of the progress or effectiveness of BPR implementations at the universities. An Information Security Management System concentrates policies, procedures, guidelines, and resources for joint management, on the protection of information assets of organizations. This study proposed an Information System Security Framework (ISSM) for Ethiopian Higher Educational Institution (EHEI). It integrates the phases of BPR and stages of ISO/IEC 27001 aligned together to meet the universities mission and vision as described in Table 1. Vulnerability Assessment and Penetration Testing mechanism is incorporated into the model presenting the tools for practical security application. Adopting FTVETI Website and eLearning Management System as a case study for the proposed ISSM, Kali Linux has been used for penetration testing and OWASP Zed Attack Proxy (ZAP) for vulnerability scanning using the OWASP Top 10 Criteria. The result reveals that 7 out of 10 of OWASP Top 10 were passed for the website and 8 out of 10 of OWASP Top were passed for the elearning respectively. The proposed framework can serve as a guiding model for all Ethiopian Higher Educational Institution particularly public universities on how to implement security of their information systems that support both academic and administrative purposes.

Keywords: Information Security Framework, ISO/IEC 27001, BPR, Vulnerability Assessment, Higher Education

1. Introduction

IT infrastructure is also being seen increasingly as an important factor affecting a firm's competitive performance. IT infrastructure is critical to globally competing firms and to those which employ a diverse group of technologies. IT infrastructure is particularly important in facilitating the development of global virtual corporations, virtual networks of partner companies, and virtual value chains Different types of system, structure, process, and technology can be found at the universities contributing for considerable complexity in managing IT. IT can act as a strong agent for change in teaching, research and knowledge generation and transfer to society, nuclear processes at universities [1].

In fact, the Ethiopian government recognized the importance of ICT for the country's development and ICT in education is also expected to be a key catalyst for the transformation of education so as to contribute for the economic prosperity in the country [2]. However, there has been neither governance guidelines in most if not all Ethiopian Higher Educational Institution that monitor the implementation of this ICT services if its achieve its the effective performance. Having this in mind, it is evident that there is a lack of studies on these important topics for higher education. Thus, this research is deeply rooted with the main gaps that there has been no formulated and adopted Information Security Framework using ISO/IEC 27001 with Penetration Testing/ Vulnerability Assessment in Ethiopian Higher Educational Institution.

According to Ranganathan & Dhaliwal [3], BPR is a popular management tool for dealing with rapid technological and business changes. Business process reengineering (BPR) is a dramatic change that represents the overhaul of organizational structures, management systems, employee responsibilities and empowerment, performance measurements, incentive systems, skills development, and the use of information technology. Ethiopian Higher Education Institution (EHEI) embrace BPR, and many studies have been done focusing on reengineering and implementing BPR in EHEI's. However, its focuses was given to the investigation of the progress or effectiveness of BPR implementations at the universities [4].

The ISO/IEC 27000 family of standards helps organizations keep information assets secure. Using this family of standards will help your organization manage the security of assets such as financial information, intellectual property, employee details or information entrusted to you by third parties. ISO/IEC 27001 is the best-known standard in the family providing requirements for an information security management system (ISMS) [5]. An Information Security Management System

December 31, 2018

concentrates policies, procedures, guidelines, and resources for joint management, on the protection of information assets of organizations. In addition, ISMS consolidates a systematic approach for establishing, implementing, operating, monitoring, revising and improving information security, in line with strategic business goals [6].

2. Related Works

Joshi and Singh [7] proposed information Security Risk Management Framework for University Computing Environment. The research analyzed the security threats specifically evolve in the University's network, and with consideration of these issues, proposed risk assessment framework for University computing environment. The proposed framework reduces the risk of security breach by supporting three phase activities; the first phase assesses the threats and vulnerabilities in order to identify the weak point in an educational environment, the second phase focuses on the highest risk and creates actionable remediation plan, the third phase of risk assessment model recognizes the vulnerability management compliance requirement in order to improve University's security position. The proposed framework was applied to the Vikram University Ujjain Indias, computing environment and the evaluation result showed the proposed framework enhances the security level of University campus network. and repeatable risk analysis in a realistic and affordable manner. Additionally, the same researcher also conducted an entitled Security Testing and Assessment of Vulnerability Scanners in Quest of Current Information Security Landscape explains the defense measures to secure the application significantly. The results of web application evaluation identify the most challenging vulnerabilities for the scanner to detect, and compare the effectiveness of scanners. It describes a web application intended to be used to evaluate the efficiency of Netsparker, Acunetix, and Burp Suite web application vulnerability scanners [8]

Mozzaquatro et al. [9] proposed an ontology-based cybersecurity framework for the internet of things that focus on the improvement of IoT cybersecurity from an ontological analysis, proposing appropriate security services adapted to the threats. The researcher had proposed an ontology-based cybersecurity framework using knowledge reasoning for IoT, composed of two approaches: (1) design time, which provides a dynamic method to build security services through the application of a model-driven methodology considering the existing enterprise processes; and (2) run time, which involves monitoring the IoT environment, classifying threats and vulnerabilities, and actuating in the environment ensuring the correct adaptation of the existing services. Two validation approaches demonstrate the feasibility of our concept.

Kassa [10] also proposed an information system security audit ontological framework that consists of three major levels: (A) The first level illustrates the organization's assets and its security objective, (b) the second level of the framework depicts the measurements of severity of attack with the stated value of threats, and (c) the third level of the ontology presents the required controls, which are shown as physical, administrative and logical controls for the business requirements (CIA and E2RCA2). The framework and its approach to quantitative implementation were illustrated, explained and measured based on concepts from ISO 27001. The proposed framework is able to measure the following key elements of security audit implementation: (A) Determining and evaluating the business information assets, containers and their categorization, (b) Identifying and evaluating vulnerability and threat levels of the information assets, (C) Determining the value of risk based on the severity of vulnerability and threats and (D) Measuring the impacts of risk based on the probability of occurrence.

Negara et al. [11] conduct a review of the security framework of information technology will be presented in this paper. The research will review some of the recommended frameworks for the security of information technology development based on cloud computing such as European Network and Information Security Agency (ENISA), Cloud Security Alliance (CSA), National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST).

Hasnaoui [12] proposed an information security toolkit namely URMIS (University Risk Management Information System) based on multi agent systems and integrating with existing information security frameworks and standards, to enhance the security of universities information systems. It has, therefore, become necessary to run into for an integrated approach with a proactive perspective to avoid risks and treat them without compromising the information systems. In the third section the toolkit URMIS was proposed, and the multi agent system was introduced. Akour and Alsmadi [13] conducted a vulnerability assessment on Websites of universities in Jordan using passive penetration testing methods to ensure a constructive testing methodology. Results showed that a significant number of those evaluated universities have critical or severe level vulnerabilities. Security attacks or attackers can be relatively easily exploiting such vulnerabilities

3. ISS Framework for EHEI

Higher Educational Institution in Ethiopia established an ICT Directorate office, with the same supervisory level as Dean of Colleges, Faculty, and Institute. It has been established a university wide ICT Infrastructure and built capacity to serve the University core processes and outreach the external community with required ICT consultancy services and other research/development requirements. Most Ethiopian Universities ICT Directorate composed of five sub department namely Network Infrastructure and Services, Teaching -Learning Technology, Business Application Administration & Development, Maintenance & Support Service, Training and Consultancy [14].

According to ISO [5], ISO/IEC 27001 specifies the requirements for establishing, implementing, maintaining and continually improving an information security management system (ISMS). The ISMS presents a systematic approach to keep sensitive information secure. It manages people, processes and IT systems through applying risk management processes. It is implementation it composed six (6) important steps namely: (A) Define information security policy, (B) Define information security policy, (C) Perform a risk assessment, (D) Manage the identified risk, (E) Select controls to be implemented, and (F) Implement controls. BPR is the Process Reengineering Life Cycle (PRLC). It is a six-stage methodology akin to others in the industry for companies to follow during BPR projects. The six sequential stages include (A) Envision new processes, (B) Initiate change, (C) Process diagnosis, (D) Process redesign, (E) Reconstruction and (F) Process monitoring.

Figure 1: ISSM for EHEI

Figure 1 shows the Information System Security Framework for Ethiopian Higher Educational Institution. It integrates the phases of BPR and stages of ISO/IEC 27001 aligned together to meet the universities mission and vision as described in Table 1. Vulnerability Assessment and Penetration Testing mechanism is incorporated into the model presenting the tools for practical security application. External application from the cloud and the Internet of things are also considered as it poses threats, attacks, and vulnerabilities not only in internally but also an external source. Confidentiality, integrity, and availability are basic requirements for business information security and provide the maintenance requirements of the business thereby it is necessary to be considered in the development of the framework.

Table 1: Direct Aligned for BPR and ISO/IEC for ISSM

Phases	BPR	ISO/IEC 27001
Problem Identification	Envision New Processes	Define Information Security Policy
Proposed Solution	Initiate Change	Define the Information Security Policy
Design and Assessment	Process Diagnosis Process Redesign	Perform a risk assessment
Adoption and Migration	Reconstruction	Select Controls to be implemented
Supervision and Checking	Process Monitoring	Implemented Controls

4. Experimentation

Federal Technical and Vocational Education and Training Institute (FTVETI) was established in 2011 by The Council of Ministers Proclamation 245/2011 as a higher learning institution with a goal of producing highly professional and technically efficient TVET teachers and leaders. The driving force for establishing FTVETI, among other things, was that there was no institution to train competent and sufficient technical and vocational teachers and leaders based on the outcome based system and occupational standards. Currently, it offers both undergraduate (bachelor’s degree) and postgraduate (Master’s degree) program in Automotive, Building, Road, Water, Information and Communication Technology, Electrical and Control, Electronics and Communications, Manufacturing, Rolling Stock and Surveying [15]. In order to simulate the proposed ISSM framework, the institution website of FTVETI (www.ftveti.edu.et) as reflected in Figure 2 and its e-learning management system enterprise application (elearning.ftveti.edu.et) as reflected in Figure 3 has been conducted a vulnerability assessment and penetration testing. Penetration Testing is a method used to evaluate the security of a system or computer network by performing an attack simulation. In the OWASP methodology, Web Application Security Testing focuses only on the security of web applications, where the process involves actively analyzing web applications, to find weaknesses, technical defects, and weaknesses [16].

Figure 2: FTVETI Website

Figure 3: FTVETI e-learning management system

According to OWASP [16], the security community released its annual report in 2015 capturing the top risks in web application development as a combination of the probability of an event and its consequence. The list of the top risks in web applications is as follows: (A1) Injection, (A2) Broken Authentication and Session Management (XSS), (A3) Cross Site Scripting (XSS), (A4) Insecure Direct Object References, (A5) Security Misconfiguration, (A6) Sensitive Data Exposure, (A7) Missing Function Level Access Control, (A8) Cross Site Request Forgery (CSRF), (A9) Using Components with Known Vulnerabilities and (A10) Unvalidated Redirects and Forward.

Kali Linux has been used for penetration testing and OWASP Zed Attack Proxy (ZAP) for vulnerability scanning in security weaknesses such as cross site scripting (XSS), malware, SQL injection, and many other Vulnerabilities. Kali Linux is a Debian-derived Linux distribution designed for digital forensics and penetration testing with the interface as reflected in Figure 4. It is maintained and funded by Offensive Security. The OWASP Zed Attack Proxy (ZAP) is one of the world's most popular free security tools and is actively maintained by hundreds of international volunteers. It can help you automatically find security vulnerabilities in your web applications while you are developing and testing your applications. It's also a great tool for experienced pentesters to use for manual security testing [17].

December 31, 2018

Figure 4: Kali Linux with OWASP ZAP installed

OWASP ZAP User Interface as shown in Figure 5 allows security tester to check some vulnerability of a website or any web enterprise application by inserting the URL and perform a scanning attack.

Figure 5: OWASP ZAP User Interface

The result of vulnerability assessment of both FTVETI Website and eLearning management system through the OWASP Top 10 using Kali Linux and OWASP ZAP were shown in Table 2. It reveals that 7 out of 10 of OWASP Top 10 were passed for the website and 8 out of 10 of OWASP Top were passed for the eLearning respectively.

Table 2: Vulnerability Assessment of FTVETI Website and eLearning using OWASP Top 10

No	OWASP Top 10	FTVETI Website	FTVETI eLearning
A1	Injection	Passed	Passed
A2	Broken Authentication and Session Management	Passed	Passed
A3	Cross-Site Scripting (XSS)	Passed	Passed
A4	Insecure Direct Object References	Failed	Passed
A5	Security Misconfiguration	Passed	Failed
A6	Sensitive Data Exposure	Failed	Passed
A7	Missing Function Level Access Control	Passed	Passed
A8	Cross-Site Request Forgery (CSRF)	Passed	Passed
A9	Using Components with known vulnerabilities	Failed	Failed
A10	Using Components with known vulnerabilities	Passed	Passed

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

Vulnerability Assessment and Penetration Testing is an important security mechanism tools every organization should undertake including higher educational institution. The proposed framework can serve as a guiding model for all

December 31, 2018

Ethiopian Higher Educational Institution particularly public universities on how to implement security of their information systems that support both academic and administrative purposes. Finally, it is recommended that other vulnerability scanning tools can be utilized to test the framework by integrating different penetration testing software with ISO, BPR, and OWASP.

References

- i. S. Sarkar, *The role of information and communication technology (ICT) in higher education for the 21st century. Science, Vol 1, Issue 1, pp. 30-41, 2012.*
- ii. T. Anberbi, *Survey of the Use e-Learning in Higher Education in Ethiopia, 2015*
- iii. C. Ranganathan, C., and J.S. Dhaliwal, *A survey of business process reengineering practices in Singapore. Information and Management, 39(2). 2001*
- iv. H. Sibhato, A.P. Singh., *Evaluation on BPR Implementation in Ethiopian Higher Education Institutions. Global Journal of Management and Business Research, 12(11). 2012.*
- v. ISO, *An Overview of ISO / IEC 27000 family of Information Security Management System, 2015(November).*
- vi. Ostec, *ISO 27000, first steps with the standard. Retrieved from <https://ostec.blog/en/general/first-steps-iso-27000>. 2018.*
- vii. C. Joshi, *“Security Testing and Assessment of Vulnerability Scanners in Quest of Current Information Security Landscape,” no. July, 2016*
- viii. U. K. Singh and C. Joshi, *“Information Security Risk Management Framework for University Computing Environment,” Int. J. Netw. Secur., vol. 191912, no. 55, pp. 742–751, 2017*
- ix. B. A. Mozzaquatro, C. Agostinho, D. Goncalves, J. Martins, and R. Jardim-Goncalves, *“An ontology-based cybersecurity framework for the internet of things,” Sensors (Switzerland), vol. 18, no. 9, pp. 1–20, 2018*
- x. S. Kassa, *“Information Systems Security Audit: An Ontological Framework,” ISACA J., vol. 5, pp. 1–8, 2016.*
- xi. E. S. Negara and R. Andryani, *“A Review : Security Framework Information Technology for University Based on Cloud Computing A Review : Security Framework Information Technology for University Based on Cloud Computing,” no. February, 2014*
- xii. S. E. L. Hasnaoui, *“Toward an Effective Information Security Risk Management of Universities ’ Information Systems Using Multi Agent Systems , Itil , Iso 27002 , Iso 27005,” vol. 5, no. 6, pp. 114–118, 2014.*
- xiii. M. Akour and T. Alsmadi, *Vulnerability Assessments: A Case Study of Jordanian Universities, International Conference on Open Source Software Computing, September 10-13, 2015, Amman, Jordan.*
- xiv. MOE, *A Guideline for Modularization to Ethiopian Higher Education Institutions Addi Ababa. Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia, 2015*
- xv. FTVETI, *Federal TVET Institute Official Website. Retrieved from www.ftveti.edu.et, 2018.*
- xvi. OWASP, *OWASP Top 10, Retrieved from https://www.owasp.org/index.php/Top_10_2013-Top_10, 2013*
- xvii. OWASP, *OWASP Zed Attacks Projects. Retrieved from https://www.owasp.org/index.php/OWASP_Zed_Attack_Proxy_Project, 2018..*